

TeRRRitoria

Policy Recommendations

for embedding RRI into the R&I development cycle

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824565

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They should be referenced as: Eleftherakis G. and Michali M. (2022) “Recommendations for responsible regional innovation”, South-East European Research Centre (SEERC), Thessaloniki, Greece, doi:10.5281/zenodo.6362133

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The TeRRItoria

policy recommendations address the integration of RRI principles and dimensions into regional R&I policies, including S3. These policies have been developed while drawing to core project activities -for example, co-design and implementation of Transformative Experiments (TEs), Mutual Learning (ML) activities- as well as to specific theoretical concepts (RRI, Territorial RRI framework, RIS approach, Interactive Learning theory). With particular reference to the core project activities, relevant data were collected and experiences were shared in the respective WPs (e.g. WP4 - Co-design of transformative experiments, WP5 - Implementing the Transformative Experiments), as well as by employing the various WP7 tools: research diaries, blog posts, ML meetings. Data collected were coded and thematically analysed –for extracting the main lessons learned throughout the project as well as the policy recommendations (for more details on these methodological procedures, see D7.1 (Michali & Eleftherakis, 2022)). The main objectives and consequent contribution of the policy recommendations developed within TeRRItoria refer to: i) enhancing the development of responsible regional policies; ii) adding the element of the multitude of visions, values and stakeholder perceptions in S3 (a core element of RRI); iii) adding a place-based approach in RRI (which is an inherent feature of S3); iv) fostering a smart, inclusive and sustainable growth, paving the way for a smooth transition to S4+.

The TeRRItoria recommendations address all stages entailed by a policy's lifespan and are grouped as follows:

A

Recommendations on how to integrate effectively RRI principles into the design stage of regional policies and S3 (including EDP); particular emphasis is placed on ways to genuinely and openly engage the public and the various QH representatives, thus achieving an effective co-creation process that fosters the representation of a multitude of visions and interests.

B

Recommendations addressing the implementation stage of regional policies, highlighting how the four RRI dimensions can shape the actual content and realisation of regional innovation policies and S3.

C

Recommendations for integrating RRI principles and dimensions into the monitoring and evaluation stage of regional policies and S3.

D

Overall suggestions and aspects to be considered while attempting to integrate RRI principles in regional policies, including S3.

E

Suggestions for enhancing the sustainability of RRI-driven regional policies and their results/impact achieved.

A

Recommendations for integrating RRI principles into the design stage of regional innovation policies and S3 (including EDP)

The following recommendations address the integration of RRI principles and dimensions into the design and development stage of the regional innovation policies. Drawing to i) the co-creation procedures taken place within TeRRitoria, and ii) partners' overall reflections and experiences during the project lifespan, insights have been primarily gained on how to achieve an inclusive engagement, fostering the development of collaborative R&I agendas. Concurrently, valuable insights have been acquired with respect to developing these collaborative agendas in an open and transparent way. As for integrating RRI specifically in the development/co-design stage of S3 –i.e. EDP– TeRRitoria partners similarly shared their thoughts and a few 'hints' based on their experience. Therefore, the TeRRitoria recommendations for RRI integration into the design stage of regional innovation policies and S3 are thematically grouped as follows: A.1) **recommendations for inclusive and collaborative R&I agendas**; A.2) **recommendations for open and transparent R&I agendas**; A.3) **recommendations for RRI integration into EDP**.

Inclusive and collaborative R&I agendas

R&I (and S3) agendas characterised as inclusive and collaborative are the ones integrating a multitude of perspectives, visions, and interests. Their collaborative development takes place through co-creation procedures among the various actors of an R&I ecosystem –who also get engaged in new forms of communication and cooperation. Inclusive and collaborative R&I agendas can be developed by taking into account the following:

Collaborative R&I agendas can be developed by involving various stakeholder groups in the policy design through consultation activities

- Consultations and reciprocal communication can be realised through various ‘tools’ and activities, indicatively referring to: citizen assemblies, co-creation labs, foresight exercises entailing stakeholders’ participation, consultations applying the Delphi method, World Cafes etc. All these methods and activities can particularly favour the participation and consequent engagement of citizens (further details on such activities can be found in the [Action Catalogue](#) of the [Engage2020 EU project](#)).
- Consultation activities should be **inclusive** of all QH categories, as well as of various socio-demographic groups (including the interested minority and vulnerable groups); one should go beyond the usual ‘suspects’ and also attempt to engage the ‘hard-to-get’ audience, even if this may require more efforts and specific approaches.
- In order to mitigate the challenges accompanying inclusive engagement (e.g, geographical proximity, the profound challenge of ‘geography of discontent’ –as in McCann 2019; OECD, 2018), mitigation measures can refer to employing **blended (both virtual and physical) engagement methods**. It is recommended that such mitigation measures i) are particularly applied in the post-COVID era where relevant challenges have been augmented, and ii) consider the specific needs, potential and possibilities of the issue(s) and regions in question. (Example 1: [The virtual engagement of remote rural communities by ADR- Nord Est](#))
- The development of collaborative R&I agendas can build on the challenge-based approach, thus ensuring that regional needs and problems are genuinely considered.
- In order to engage citizens, who have been repeatedly proven to be the most hard-to-get audience, the territory can firstly initiate the appropriate **capacity-building activities (addressing both citizens and the regional authorities in charge)**. In this way, particularly the public firstly gets familiarised with the target topics, and then gets gradually and steadily involved –something probably resulting to fewer cases of ‘withdrawing’.

- Capacity building can refer to short-term activities (e.g. single training events on responsible research, on R&I policy-making, on regional innovation etc.) or long-term and more systematic activities (e.g. developing relevant university curricula in regional universities). Particularly tertiary education can function as a means for starting citizen engagement from the level of students; for example, asking students to participate in the drafting of Regional Operation Programs (ROPs).
 - For familiarizing citizens with R&I activities and processes, citizen science initiatives (CS) can also be organised. CS initiatives indicatively refer to R&I projects where R&I results are collaboratively translated to solutions delivered to the communities' needs, to projects fostering science and STEM literacy, to initiatives entailing biological and wildlife recording, initiatives addressing the topic of 'personal data' and the rights to privacy online etc. (further details and training material on such initiatives can be found in the [EU-Citizen.Science platform](#)).
 - Capacity-building activities can be accompanied by the provision of incentives to civil society and citizens in order to foster their participation even further; for instance, financial support to Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) would be such an incentive, since they often lack the organisational resources to finance the involvement of their staff in engagement activities.
- It is strongly advised **that different fields and disciplines** (both from the academia and the business sector) are represented in the consultation activities; one should avoid involving representatives coming exclusively from the STEM-oriented academic fields and business sectors. In this way, a multitude of visions is represented and both enriched and differentiated input to the policy design is gained.
 - Target stakeholders should be engaged from **early in the design process**. Early 'upstream' engagement contributes to ensuring that the R&I positive and negative impacts are better governed and exploited at a much earlier stage. Concurrently, the engagement of the public is achieved before opinions become polarised and hardened and policies are predetermined.
 - Along with the early 'upstream' engagement, it is recommended that a systematic **follow-up communication** with the stakeholders is pursued (if possible, follow-up synergies as well); it is then easier to retain or even extend the regional connections, and build networks. (Example 2: Retaining stakeholder connections in RCM through systematic and follow-up communication)
 - Stakeholders' motivation and consequent commitment are necessary. These can be fostered by engaging them in the **construction of the territory's vision**. With such strategies, involved stakeholders can more easily feel 'problem-owners'. (Example 3: Engaging stakeholders in the socio-economic analysis of Gabrovo).

- It is advised that **new coalitions of QH actors** are developed during co-design; coalitions of actors representing different institutions, fields, interests and perspectives signify enriched feedback, while their in-between interaction brings at the surface regional issues otherwise not becoming evident. Concurrently, coalitions of representatives of different regional institutions can contribute to addressing siloed policy thinking.
 - New coalitions can be formed through various consultation meetings, events, or workshops. **Regional Open Innovation Platforms (ROIPs)** can particularly create an encouraging environment. (Example 4: The Emilia Romagna Open Innovation Platform)
- Overall, the involvement of actors can be widened through the following: capitalising on **organisational mapping**; capitalising on **territorial networks** (strategic networking); providing **incentives** to the various stakeholders in order to participate in the R&I processes. (Example 5: Providing to the RCM stakeholders a GEP template as an incentive related to eligibility in Horizon Europe)

A.2

Open and transparent R&I agendas

Along with ensuring that R&I agendas are developed in a collaborative and inclusive way, their overall development process should also be communicated in an open and transparent way to any interested stakeholder. Openness and transparency can be fostered by taking into account the following recommendations:

- The design processes of regional R&I policies can be **open and transparent** to the wider public through open consultation initiatives. In this case, the public and interested stakeholders can be genuinely involved in the construction of their territory's vision, regional agendas are not hijacked by established interests and 'experts', while R&I policy-making overall integrates principles of social responsibility –which stands for ensuring that there is balance between economic growth and the welfare of society and the environment.
- Transparency should similarly exist in the **communication of results**; in this case, more

feedback is received and follow-up regional discussions are triggered. Stakeholders consequently feel that their participation is valuable, rather a means to legitimise the content of regional R&I processes.

- This kind of transparency can be ensured if abiding by the **open research / open scholarship** principles. Von Schomberg (2019) defined open scholarship as sharing knowledge and data as early as possible in the research process in open collaboration with all relevant knowledge actors. Adapting this to the design of regional innovation policies, details on the first co-design steps and the first results acquired are shared both with the relevant ‘knowledgeable’ actors (e.g. regional policy-makers) as well as with the public and interested stakeholders.
- The **appropriate science communication** is an integral part of transparent design processes and corresponding results; effective communication channels need to be established with the target stakeholders, building on rendering the RRI and policy language understandable for the audiences.
 - Indicatively, the appropriate science communication should **avoid scientific jargon** when addressing the lay public, while additionally focusing on the simplicity and clarity of the message.
 - When communicating in local languages, **dynamic translation equivalents** for RRI terms should be assured.

A.3

RRI integration into the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP)

EDP constitutes the consultation stage of S3, where its co-development and co-design take place. As previously mentioned, TeRRitoria partners shared their experiences in attempting to integrate RRI into the EDP stage of their regional S3, as well as their overall reflections on what relevant attempts should consider in order to be successful. In more details:

- Principles of **inclusiveness** and the **QH approach** should be integrated in the EDP, so that key regional stakeholders are included. After all, owing to the place-based approach of S3, local engagement is necessary.
 - **Inclusive EDP** refers to engaging the following stakeholder categories: Academia (both public and private universities, research centres, education-oriented institutions); Industry (both the public sector and private sector, both large and smaller firms, innovative start-ups and SMEs; social entrepreneurs; incumbents and firms in the new economy, trade unions); Government actors (local, regional and national authorities, policy-makers, EU representatives); Citizens (civil society, social communities, users, end-beneficiaries of the new system, citizens' associations, NGOs).
 - Concrete recommendations for engaging the various stakeholder groups have been listed under the previous sub-section addressing collaborative and inclusive R&I agendas.
- It is recommended that the **benefits of RRI, especially Public Engagement (PE), on EDP outcomes are promoted**; it should be systematically highlighted that the integration of RRI principles in EDP facilitates the unleashing of local creativity, thus ensuring greater competitiveness and economic growth.
- EDP processes and results should be communicated in an open and transparent way; in other words, it is recommended not to have **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) during the discovery phase** for ensuring that the knowledge that is relevant and beneficial to the society is shared as openly and as early as possible.
- While realising EDP, the interaction among the different QH layers can be exploited based on the **concept of 'related variety'** (Frenken et al, 2007; Boschma and Iammarino 2009); knowledge from existing sectors (e.g. from the scientific sectors) can be spilled-over to new paths (e.g. industrial paths) for maximising regional development prospects
 - While moving from rhetoric to well-functioning policies, the experiences of actors having a rich body of knowledge on what works and what does not is even more important. Therefore, the knowledge spill-over suggested by 'related variety' could follow various directions, other than 'spilling' knowledge only from the scientific to the industry sector. A notable example refers to the relation between universities and community; in most cases, the focus has been on what community colleges lack compared to universities, e.g. the ability to publish internationally. Drawing, however, to the experience gained out of some TeRRitoria TEs (e.g. the Trondelag TE, for more details see D5.3), universities can learn much from community colleges on how to achieve local relevance in higher education, as well as how to boost local innovation.

Example 1: The virtual engagement of remote rural communities by ADR- Nord Est

ADR-Nord Est representatives came across the challenge of having to engage some remote rural (mountain) communities during the COVID-19 outbreak, where physical events were not allowed. Given the fact that these communities were not accustomed in online and virtual engagement methods, bilateral phone interviews were conducted, even if being considerably time-consuming. Additionally, ADR-Nord Est representatives have shared their thoughts about continuing to engage these communities by providing them assistance with the use of the brokerage platform.

Example 2: Retaining stakeholder connections in RCM through systematic and follow-up communication

After every event and workshop organised, the RCM team would further communicate and engage the attendees. Relevant follow-up activities referred to: short surveys through questionnaires; completing Google forms and working on collaborative Google docs for collecting further feedback and providing attendees with the opportunity to express their perspective and their ideas without any time limitations; invitations to join two different Groups of Interest/Action groups (Action Group 1: *Female Career Progression*, Action Group 2: *Internal Regulations of the RPOs towards gender equality*.)

Example 3: Engaging stakeholders in the socio-economic analysis of Gabrovo

The co-design phase of Gabrovo ended with a stakeholder summit in late June 2020, where 50 participants, representing all QH categories, participated. The Gabrovo team presented a socio-economic analysis of the city and the province, along with a SWOT analysis with a 10-year horizon. All findings and conclusions emerging from the summit were summarised in a document, published at the municipal website and made available for discussion and provision of feedback within one month after the summit.

Example 4: The Emilia Romagna Open Innovation Platform

ART-ER developed a participatory advisory process to engage regional innovation actors and stakeholders to comment on the first S3 draft; this consultation engaged various actors of the regional innovation ecosystem, meaning Clust-ER, Technopoles, Research and Innovation Centers etc. The consultation was held on-line through the use of the brand new EROI (Emilia-Romagna Open Innovation) platform, allowing the use of 2 different tools: a survey, and posts/comments on the draft. The platform was set up through a co-design process and it's intended to be the virtual space, community and marketplace for the innovation that happens throughout the Emilia-Romagna Region.

Example 5: Providing to the RCM stakeholders a GEP template as an incentive related to eligibility in Horizon Europe

The RCM TE managed to attract a big number of interested stakeholders, mainly owing to the nature of the TE (i.e. gender issues and equality). In order to extend the sample of engaged stakeholders, the RCM team provided the regional stakeholders with a valuable incentive; the regional Gender Equality Plan (GEP) co-developed would function as a GEP template with numerous indicative strategic areas and action points. In other words, regional R&I actors could use this GEP as a basis for creating their own self-tailored GEP, and particularly within the context of having GEPs as an eligibility criterion for Horizon Europe.

B

Recommendations for integrating the RRI principles and dimensions into the implementation stage of regional innovation policies and S3

This sub-section outlines how RRI can be integrated into the actual content of regional R&I policies and S3 –and thus to their implementation. Policy recommendations have been formed with reference to the integration of each one of the four dimensions.

Anticipation

S3 and other regional innovation policies can enhance anticipation by:

- Including risk-management plans, analysing possible long-term impacts.
- Realising foresight exercises (e.g. future scenarios exercises) and forecasting, so that policy decision-making is based on a set of logical and anticipated assumptions.
- Developing anticipatory governance mechanisms, by integrating features/principles of technology assessment.
- Employing theories of change when setting new goals.
- Consulting mission-oriented approaches –in this way RRI is also integrated into regional innovation and S3 in a sustainable way.

- Mission-oriented innovation includes any new or improved technological, social and organisational solution (product, process or service) that aims to respond to one or several of the grand societal challenges (missions) (OECD, 2021)

Inclusiveness

The inclusiveness of S3 and other regional innovation policies can be enhanced by:

- Ensuring that the **R&I agendas developed are truly collaborative**, building on intra-regional collaboration. Concurrently, it should be ensured that the different actors' perspectives and interests are represented.

- The inclusion of these differentiated interests can be realised if abiding by the engagement suggestions listed under sub-section 3.1.

- When attempting to include different actors' perspectives and interests, **potential conflicts** may emerge; these should be managed at all times and **turn into sources of knowledge**. As for ways of managing the conflicts, these refer to presenting the target topic as a win-win situation to all sides, or a priori initiating something that is beneficial to all sides –even for different reasons.

- Capitalising on **inter-regional collaboration** and feedback for optimum implementation of the new policies; inclusiveness is fostered owing to the integration of differentiated perspectives of different territories, while additional value and feedback is gained from the diversity existing among the different regional systems. ([Example 6: Dialogues of Responsible Regions, organised by EURADA](#))

- Inserting in R&I policies and S3 the **principles of (participatory) value-sensitive design (VSD)**.

- VSD brings human values to the forefront of the technical design process, and suggests that technologists, designers, business leaders and others involved in developing technology should have strategies for identifying and incorporating human values into the design and development process. Value-sensitive design aims to consider the values not only of the users, but of all others impacted by the technologies –regardless of whether those individuals will ever actually use the technologies (Himma & Tavani, 2008).

- Ensuring that a reference to equality principles and inclusiveness is included in the S3/ regional policy and its strategic document. ([Example 7: Integrating gender equality principles and objectives in the S3 strategic document of the RCM](#))

A final note refers to taking the concept of inclusiveness a step further; in this case, inserting the element of 'inclusion' in regional innovation policies and S3 signifies that the policy itself is characterized by **societal desirability**, and can contribute to addressing societal challenges. For more relevant and precise recommendations, the **smart directionality approach** can be employed:

- The smart directionality approach indicates that knowledge production and exploitation should embrace societal goals and challenges, and that a bigger focus should be placed on the responsible use of knowledge and research results for societal purposes (Mazzucato, 2016).

Example 6: Dialogues of Responsible Regions, organised by EURADA

EURADA launched the Dialogues of Responsible Regions, constituting monthly webinar meetings (dialogues) on the topics of RRI and S3. These monthly webinars functioned as an opportunity to get to know the diverse R&I ecosystems of the various regions, to exchange feedback on their policies and provide suggestions for RRI integration and citizen engagement in the regional innovation policies. Indicative topics discussed refer to: “Giving citizens a seat at the table of R&I regional policymaking. (Lombardy region, TRANSFORM)” “Can we measure the “wellbeing” of RIS with the dimensions of RRI and the MoRRI indicators?”, “Innovation Policy Labs: the example of smart grids in Valencia”.

Example 7: Integrating gender equality principles and objectives in the S3 strategic document of the RCM

The RCM team attempted to make their upcoming S3 more inclusive by suggesting the insertion of gender equality principles and objectives in the S3 strategic document.

Example of gender principles:

“ [the S3] Encourages technology, research and innovation investments that harness women’s potential and work towards gender equality”

Examples of objectives:

“Increase of women involved in STEM sciences“

“Increase of women starting innovative start-ups“

Reflexivity

The following points can contribute to fostering the reflexivity of S3 and regional innovation policies:

- While implementing S3, the individuals in charge will be benefitted by creating and exploiting **reflexive spaces**; these spaces allow taking a ‘step back’, and reflecting on the activities realised and their success before starting new ones. Such a rationale can also coincide with the **principles of formative evaluation** (Hall & Hall, 2004).
- It is recommended that the strategies are **‘mirrored’ before truly implemented**; in other words, one should take into account the region’s impact on other regions, on the environment, or on different groups of citizens.
- **Critical approaches to STI and R&I** can be employed.
- **‘Self-analysis’ and ‘self-criticism’** should be made while designing and implementing such policies; feedback received should be appreciated at all times, and be accompanied by a receptive-to-change attitude.
- Reflexivity also signifies that individuals in charge of or involved in these policies also **learn from their past experiences** and, most importantly, **learn from their failures**.

Responsiveness

The responsiveness of S3 and regional innovation policies can be enhanced if the following are taken into account:

- It is necessary that S3 foresees the development of contingency plans in relation to some predicted challenges.
- **Flexibility and adaptability** should always exist by having a ‘Plan B’ in relation to some unpredicted challenges.
- It is necessary to consider that **regional policies ‘gradually’ take shape** and new variables come into play while transitioning from co-design to implementation. ([Example 8: The iterative implementation of the Trondelag TE](#))
- Responsiveness also signifies **keeping up with the new developments**; particularly new EU / national / local policies, priorities and directions, new scientific, technological and societal trends, as well as new societal/political pressures (e.g. on gender issues) should be considered for updating or re-adjusting the content of the policies. ([Example 9: Adding action points on sexual harassment in the RCM GEP](#); [Example 10: Aligning Gabrovo TE to the Green Deal](#))
- Based on new emerging strategic directions, detecting appropriate **change agents** can be beneficial; they can pave the way towards the new directions and systematically engage more regional actors owing to their influence.

Example 8: The iterative implementation of the Trondelag TE

Covering all higher education activities, conducted by NTNU and all stakeholders in the remote areas, allowed for a broad choice of possible experiments to be co-created with different sets of stakeholders –something resulting to an iterative process for the TE implementation and to new variables coming into play while transitioning from co-design to implementation. After having decided on three specific experiments, fresh graduates, students, and teachers having experience with collaboration with remote areas were identified. This back and forth between adding new stakeholders and involving them and adjusting the experimental focus continued during the whole experiment. At the same time, a limited number of stakeholders withdrew for external reasons, which helped to further define the experiments' scope.

Example 9: Adding action points on sexual harassment in the RCM GEP

While the strategic area addressing sexual harassment in R&I organisations originally received a 'standard' attention in the GEP (not a lot of concerns existed in the region at that time), a few months later the belated #MeToo in Greece suddenly gave rise to multiple concerns and accusation throughout the entire country. The corresponding strategic area was thus enriched with numerous action points and suggestions for addressing sexual harassment in the organisations.

Example 10: Aligning Gabrovo TE to the Green Deal

During July 2020, local stakeholders were invited to take part in a conference about the future of the EU cohesion policy in the period 2021-2027 in the context of the EU Green Deal. The event aimed to ensure the alignment of the vision of the local strategy to the respective priorities on national and EU level. The discussion addressed how 'green' measures and available instruments could be used for regional development. After this meeting, a thematic focus group 'Economy, innovations and human capital' was established, and was tasked with designing the economic policy within the Plan of Integrated Development of the city, thus providing the basis for developing S3 until 2027. All these activities were embedded within the Gabrovo TE.

C

Recommendations for integrating RRI principles and dimensions into the monitoring and evaluation stage of regional innovation policies and S3

The following recommendations can be considered for: C.1) *conducting an RRI-driven monitoring and evaluation of regional innovation policies and S3 (and their results)*; C.2) *monitoring and evaluating the RRI-related impact of the policies*.

C.1

RRI-driven monitoring and evaluation

- Monitoring and evaluation **should not assess only the S3/R&I intervention *per se***, but also the potential impacts it can generate.
 - The relevant monitoring and evaluation can be accompanied by **ethics reviews**, entailing codes of conduct for assessing the impacts of the policies on society.
 - The evaluation criteria for the funding of new R&I projects can integrate elements of **social impact assessment (including societal readiness level)**.

- Principles of social responsibility can be integrated into the S3 impact assessment
 - As previously mentioned, social responsibility attempts to ensure that there is balance between economic growth and the welfare of society and the environment.
- The integration of the ‘**intervention logic**’ highly contributes to inserting elements of anticipation into evaluation, since it indicates the necessity of having a clear and well-thought-out understanding how planned policy actions are expected to lead to desired outcomes.

C.2

Monitoring and evaluating the RRI impact

- Evaluation criteria for the funding of R&I projects could also assess the impact specifically related to the RRI keys (i.e. **RRI-related funding criteria**).
 - In this aforementioned case, an appropriate **RRI-oriented capacity-building of the evaluators** is advised to take place.
- **Awards and accreditation systems** for S3-funded initiatives can be developed, indicating and acknowledging the applicability of RRI principles and the relevant impact achieved.
- **Ex-post evaluation** can be accompanied by **RRI-tailored evaluation indicators** in order to measure whether the impact achieved by S3 implementation is RRI-oriented.

D

Overall suggestions for RRI integration into regional innovation policies and S3

This subsection outlines a few experience-based suggestions, potentially facilitating the RRI integration into regional innovation policies and S3. In more details:

- The **QH approach** can be integrated in the **governance model of S3** as well; in other words, people responsible for overseeing its implementation and monitoring can represent all helixes, thus broadening the territory's vision.
 - The development of such governance models should however take place with caution; their composition may be important, but ultimately **their activities constitute an added value** and contribute to avoiding ticking-the-box exercises.
- **Regional size matters** and particularly urban and rural areas follow different paths. Such regional features should be considered when developing (RRI-driven) regional policies.
- **Changes to regional structures**, including political shifts, may create implications; one should be prepared for effects of such changes on regional policies.
- While attempting to change and ameliorate the content of regional innovation policies, some regions can undertake the role of change agents and **function as 'test-beds'** for the integration of RRI principles to S3.
- The commitment of a **consolidated local government**, already experienced from the launching of the previous S3, should be ensured for effectively integrating RRI and applying any relevant policy recommendations.
- RRI integration in S3 and regional policies can also take place within **the rationale of the five RRI keys** (Public Engagement, Science Education, Gender Equality, Ethics, and Open Access). In this case, each region –depending on its needs– can indicate and suggest **RRI-tailored funding**. Indicatively:

- Funding of R&I actions that favour female participation and inclusiveness (gender+ approach)
- Funding of science education projects (STEM/STEAM)
- Funding for the establishment of living labs, science shops and open laboratories
- RRI keys could also be capitalised within the context of spatial and urban planning, for instance participatory spatial planning, gender spatial planning.

E

Suggestions for enhancing the sustainability of RRI-driven regional policies and their results

The immediate step after the implementation of a regional policy refers to ensuring the results' sustainability. The TEs' implementation and the experiences exchanged among project partners have provided valuable ideas on ways to ensure sustainability. The following points constitute suggestions towards enhancing the sustainability of RRI-driven regional policy actions. In more details:

- A gradual **intra-regional and inter-regional scaling** of the policies' results is necessary.
- Finding an **actor in charge of 'anchoring'** the results is a prerequisite.
 - **Official bodies** are considerable allies for undertaking this role and contributing to the continuation of achieved results. ([Example 11: RCM and the regional Committee on Gender Equality](#))
 - **Informal organisations** and communities of practices can also contribute to a genuine anchoring (and, occasionally, to more innovative governance).
- **Political commitment** is vital for sustainability; it speeds up all the implementation processes and then contributes to a widespread uptake.
- A systematic and evidence-based **'advertising' of the RRI benefits** to regional stakeholders can highly contribute to sustainability.
- **Funding** and follow-up activities can considerably enhance the results' sustainability.
 - Emphasis is primarily placed on EU and national funding. Alternatives to this funding are private-public partnerships/funding, crowdfunding etc.
 - Having regional officers dealing with grant schemes can be beneficial, in order to speed up the process of detecting useful funding opportunities.
 - It should be reminded, however, that follow-up funding is not a panacea for everything. Regional ('improvised') actions may be more effective for an effective knowledge spill-over.

Example 11: RCM and the regional Committee on Gender Equality

In parallel with the co-creation activities, RCM established a regional Committee on Gender Equality in July 2020. This was the first step towards sustainable institutional change, as the committee will operate after the end of the TeRRitoria project and will be the main body in charge of both ‘anchoring’ the TeRRitoria results, and continuing the gender-related work in the region. The committee is appointed by the Regional Council and the deputy Regional Governor has been appointed as the President of the Committee.

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the European Union's Horizon 2020
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grant agreement No 824565

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